

Helium-4 (He-4) Quark Structure: A Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD) Perspective

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Abstract

This paper presents a detailed Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD) analysis of the quark structure in Helium-4 (He-4) using a dodecahedron framework. It examines both core quarks (up and down) and exotic quarks (top, strange, and charm), calculating energy distributions and modeling gluon interactions within the structure. The goal is to explore the stability, binding energy, and force dynamics of this quark configuration in high-energy environments such as particle colliders, neutron stars, or the early universe.

Introduction

The study of the universe has long been dominated by abstract mathematical models and theoretical frameworks, offering profound insights into the fundamental forces and particles that govern our cosmos. While mathematics serves as a powerful tool to describe and predict the behavior of matter and energy, it is essential to ground these abstractions in the study of the **actual matter** that exists within our universe. Understanding the composition, interactions, and behaviors of this matter—not just through mathematical expressions but through tangible, observable effects—provides a more holistic view of both **local** and **cosmic** phenomena.

In this work, we aim to expand our investigation of the universe by focusing not only on the theoretical constructs but also on how the **quarks, gluons**, and other fundamental particles that compose matter are organized and interact under various conditions. Our goal is to bridge the gap between abstract theory and the tangible understanding of how matter behaves, not only in familiar environments like those found on Earth but also under the extreme conditions of high-energy particle collisions, neutron stars, and the early universe.

Through this lens, we present a study of the **Helium-4 nucleus**, exploring its quark structure within a novel **dodecahedral framework**. Our model incorporates both **core quarks** (up and down) and **exotic quarks** (top, strange, and charm), which are typically observed only in high-energy physics experiments or extreme astrophysical phenomena. By studying this exotic configuration, we seek to uncover how matter behaves beyond the standard models, particularly when subjected to the immense

forces and energies that may exist in environments such as the **Large Hadron Collider (LHC)**, **neutron stars**, or the **early universe**.

This approach is driven by a need to expand our understanding of the universe **tangibly** and **practically**, focusing not only on the mathematical elegance of theoretical models but also on the **physical realities** of how quarks interact, form nuclei, and respond to extreme conditions. By examining matter in its various states—whether ordinary or exotic—we hope to offer deeper insights into the **evolution of the universe** and the forces that shape it, both within our observable horizon and in the vast regions beyond.

Ultimately, this study contributes to the broader effort of understanding the **nature of matter**, its origins, and its role in the cosmic tapestry. This pursuit is not just about refining our mathematical tools but about deepening our understanding of the universe through the **material interactions** that make up the fundamental fabric of existence.

The traditional model of protons and neutrons being represented by clusters of three quarks does not directly map onto the **dodecahedron framework**. In the dodecahedral model, quarks are arranged based on a more complex geometric symmetry, and the proton-neutron pair needs to be reimagined to fit within this structure.

Adapting the Proton and Neutron to a Dodecahedral Framework:

1. **Proton:** In the dodecahedral model, the **two up quarks (u)** and **one down quark (d)** of a proton would occupy the vertices of the dodecahedron. Instead of clustering these quarks together in a triangular form, they are distributed across the vertices, connected by **gluons** along the edges of the dodecahedron.
2. **Neutron:** Similarly, the **two down quarks (d)** and **one up quark (u)** of a neutron are also distributed among different vertices of the dodecahedron. This new distribution allows for the complex interactions and symmetry seen in the dodecahedron model.

To represent the **UP, UP, DOWN**, and **EXOTIC quarks** for each proton and neutron in a **dodecahedral structure**, we can assign new symbols that are both intuitive and maintain the quark structure's complexity. Next, we will expand on how to proceed:

New Symbols for Quarks in the Dodecahedron Model

1. Proton (UP, UP, DOWN):

- Use a **triangle** or **circle** symbol with internal divisions representing the **two up quarks** (u) and **one down quark** (d).
- Each vertex of the triangle or internal part of the circle can correspond to a specific position within the dodecahedron.
- **Exotic quarks** can be added as external markers or additional vertices on the dodecahedron symbol.

2. Neutron (DOWN, DOWN, UP):

- Use a **pentagon** or **hexagon** shape to differentiate it from the proton.
- Again, each internal vertex would represent one of the quarks (d, d, u), and we can add **exotic quarks** as extensions of the shape or additional markers.

Incorporating Exotic Quarks

- **Strange (s), Charm (c), Bottom (b), and Top (t) quarks will be added as external markers or additional vertices to signify their influence while keeping the core structure (UP, DOWN quarks) intact.**
- For instance, we could add these exotic quarks as smaller points or symbols attached to the main quark symbols (triangle, circle, pentagon).

Applying this to Helium's Structure

- These symbols will now represent each proton and neutron within the dodecahedral framework, with connections between them via **gluons** (represented by lines or symbols like ~).
- These new symbols will be positioned accordingly on **Layers 1, 2, and 3** of the dodecahedron to represent the interactions and internal structure.

1. Quark Configuration in He-4:

- **Core Quarks:**
 - **12 Up Quarks (u)**, each with a charge of $+2/3e$ and a mass of **335 MeV/c²**.
 - **12 Down Quarks (d)**, each with a charge of $-1/3e$ and a mass of **340 MeV/c²**.
- **Exotic Quarks:**
 - **1 Top Quark (t)**, with a charge of $+2/3e$ and a mass of **173,100 MeV/c²**.
 - **1 Strange Quark (s)**, with a charge of $-1/3e$ and a mass of **95 MeV/c²**.
 - **1 Charm Quark (c)**, with a charge of $+2/3e$ and a mass of **1,275 MeV/c²**.

Helium Nucleus Structure

Image 1.0: The red triangles represent up quarks (u), while the blue diamonds also symbolize up quarks (u) but are used to indicate a distinct position or interaction. The green circles represent down quarks (d), and the yellow circles marked with an X denote exotic quarks, which could be top (t), strange (s), or charm (c) quarks.

Helium (He-4) Quark Structure

Layer 1, 2, 3 (Core Dodecahedron):

Image 2.0: the red triangles represent up quarks (u), blue diamonds represent up quarks (u) in alternate positions, green circles denote down quarks (d), and yellow circles with "X" symbolize exotic quarks (top, strange, charm). Gluons ($\sim$) bind the quarks together within a Helium-4 nucleus.

2. Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD) Framework:

In QCD, quarks are bound together by the **strong force** mediated by gluons. The **QCD Lagrangian** describes the interactions between quarks and gluons:

$$\mathcal{L}_{QCD} = \sum_f \bar{\psi}_f (i\gamma^\mu D_\mu - m_f) \psi_f - \frac{1}{4} G_{\mu\nu}^a G^{a\mu\nu} \quad (1)$$

Where:

- ψ_f is the quark field for flavor f ,
- D_μ is the covariant derivative, and
- $G_{\mu\nu}^a$ is the gluon field strength tensor.

The gluon fields propagate between quarks, and their interaction strength is controlled by the **strong coupling constant** α_s , which evolves with energy.

Running of the Strong Coupling Constant

The strong coupling constant $\alpha_s(Q^2)$ changes with the energy scale Q^2 according to:

$$\alpha_s(Q^2) = \frac{12\pi}{(33 - 2n_f) \ln(Q^2/\Lambda_{QCD}^2)} \quad (2)$$

Where:

- n_f is the number of active quark flavors,
- $\Lambda_{QCD} \approx 200 \text{ MeV}$ is the QCD scale parameter.

At high energies, α_s becomes smaller, leading to **asymptotic freedom** (quarks behave as free particles). At lower energies, quarks are confined due to the growing strength of α_s , which leads to **quark confinement**.

3. Gluon-Mediated Quark Interactions:

Potential Energy Between Quarks

Quark-quark interactions are modeled by the **Coulomb-like potential** for short distances and a **confining potential** for large distances:

- **Short-distance potential** (Coulomb-like):

$$V(r) = -\frac{4}{3} \frac{\alpha_s(r)}{r} \quad (3)$$

- **Long-distance potential** (Confinement):

$$V(r) = \sigma r \quad (4)$$

Where $\sigma \approx 0.18 \text{ GeV}^2$ is the **string tension**, representing the energy required to separate quarks. For the dodecahedron framework, we calculate the potential between quarks at varying distances within the structure, including the interactions involving the exotic quarks.

Gluon Field Strength:

The **gluon field strength tensor** $G_{\mu\nu}^a$ quantifies the gluon interactions:

$$G_{\mu\nu}^a = \partial_\mu A_\nu^a - \partial_\nu A_\mu^a + g_s f^{abc} A_\mu^b A_\nu^c \quad (5)$$

Where A_μ^a are the gluon fields, g_s is the strong coupling constant, and f^{abc} are the structure constants of the gauge group $SU(3)_C$.

4. Energy Distribution Calculation:

Core Quarks Energy:

The energy contribution of the core quarks is calculated as follows:

$$E_{\text{core}} = (12 \times 335 \text{ MeV}) + (12 \times 340 \text{ MeV}) = 4,020 \text{ MeV} + 4,080 \text{ MeV} = 8,100 \text{ MeV} \quad (6)$$

Exotic Quarks Energy

For the exotic quarks:

$$E_{\text{top}} = 173,000 \text{ MeV}, \quad E_{\text{strange}} = 95 \text{ MeV}, \quad E_{\text{charm}} = 1,275 \text{ MeV} \quad (7)$$

The total energy for the exotic quarks is:

$$E_{\text{exotic}} = 173,000 \text{ MeV} + 95 \text{ MeV} + 1,275 \text{ MeV} = 174,370 \text{ MeV} \quad (8)$$

Total Energy (Core + Exotic Quarks)

$$E_{\text{total}} = E_{\text{core}} + E_{\text{exotic}} = 8,100 \text{ MeV} + 174,370 \text{ MeV} = 182,470 \text{ MeV} \quad (9)$$

In the dodecahedral model, quarks and their interactions play a central role, but to include leptons and bosons like gluons, we must integrate their behavior within the dodecahedron structure.

Where Leptons Fit:

- **Leptons** (such as electrons and neutrinos) interact through the weak force but do not directly participate in the strong force, unlike quarks. In the Dodecahedron Linear String Field Hypothesis (DLSFH), leptons would likely be placed outside the dodecahedral quark framework as they interact with quarks through electroweak forces.
- For instance, the **electron** in a helium atom would orbit the nucleus, interacting with the quark structure via the electromagnetic force (mediated by photons). The **neutrino** (another lepton) would also be influenced primarily by the weak force.

Where Bosons Fit:

- **Gluons** are the carriers of the strong force, binding quarks together inside protons and neutrons. In the DLSFH, the gluons could be symbolically placed at the **edges** connecting vertices (quarks), representing their role in holding quarks together.

- **Photons** (carriers of the electromagnetic force) are involved in the interactions between quarks and leptons through the electroweak force. They could be considered as part of the interactions between charged particles (quarks and leptons), mediating forces between the structure's elements.

Exotic Particles and Bosons:

- **Exotic quarks** and **bosons**, as indicated in our structure, may represent new forms of interaction beyond the Standard Model, such as dark photons or supersymmetric partners, which could be placed within or adjacent to the quark vertices to represent their interaction in higher-dimensional space.

Image 2.0: Dodecahedron Model, Helium-4 Nucleus, 2 Protons, and 2 Neutrons

Exotic Helium-4 Structure

Image 3.0: represents the Exotic Helium-4 structure. The core contains quarks (up, down, and exotic) within the nucleus, surrounded by two orbiting electrons (-e) emitting photons (γ), indicating their interaction with the nucleus.

5. Force Balance and Stability Analysis

Binding Energy and Stability

For the quark configuration to be stable, the **binding energy** between quarks must be strong enough to counterbalance the mass-energy of the exotic quarks.

The gluon-mediated interactions determine the binding energy, and the **total potential energy** of the quark system must be **negative**:

$$E_{\text{binding}} = \sum_{\text{quark pairs}} \left(-\frac{4}{3} \frac{\alpha_s(r)}{r} + \sigma r \right) \quad (10)$$

For the Helium-4 nucleus to remain stable, the binding energy must overcome the energy contribution from the top quark (173,000 MeV), which is significantly larger than the core quarks' energy.

Gluon Field Propagation

The propagation of gluons between quarks in the dodecahedron structure ensures that the quarks remain confined. Due to their high mass, exotic quarks, such as the top quark, require stronger gluon interactions, making the gluon exchange dynamics critical for stability.

6. Exotic Quark Decay and Lifetimes:

Exotic quarks, such as the **top quark**, have very short lifetimes (in the order of 10^{-25} seconds). Therefore, exotic helium nuclei with top quarks would decay quickly, producing lighter particles. The **decay channels** for exotic quarks are well-known in particle physics:

- **Top quark** decays via the weak interaction into a **W boson** and a **bottom quark**.
- **Strange and charm quarks** have longer lifetimes but would also decay into lighter quarks (up and down) via weak interactions.

7. Real-World Context: Where Exotic Helium Might Exist?

This exotic Helium-4 structure could theoretically exist in the following extreme environments:

The **Helium-4 (He-4) structure** is described as **exotic** due to the inclusion of **non-standard quarks** like the **top (t)**, **strange (s)**, and **charm (c)** quarks, which do not naturally occur in ordinary helium atoms.

7.1 Why is this Helium-4 model exotic?

1. Standard Helium-4 Composition:

- In nature, **Helium-4** consists of **two protons** and **two neutrons**, each of which is composed of the familiar **up (u)** and **down (d)** quarks. A proton contains two up quarks and one down quark, while a neutron contains two down quarks and one up quark. These particles are bound together by a strong force, mediated by gluons, forming a stable helium nucleus.

2. Inclusion of Exotic Quarks:

- In the **exotic Helium-4 model**, additional quarks such as **top**, **strange**, and **charm** are included. These quarks are not part of standard baryonic matter (like protons and neutrons) that form ordinary atoms. Instead, they are known as **exotic quarks** and only appear under extreme, high-energy conditions.
- For instance, the **top quark** is the heaviest known quark and is extremely short-lived, decaying almost immediately after its creation (on the order of 10^{-25} seconds). Similarly, **strange** and **charm quarks** typically appear in high-energy physics experiments but are absent in stable atomic nuclei.

3. Why It's Exotic:

- **Exotic matter** refers to forms of matter that include particles beyond the standard ones found in ordinary matter. In this case, introducing **top**, **strange**, and **charm quarks** into a helium nucleus is highly unconventional, as these quarks would not be found in stable, natural Helium-4. These exotic quarks would give the nucleus unusual properties, such as higher mass and different charge configurations, leading to **exotic behavior** in terms of particle interactions and decay processes.

4. Temporary Existence of Exotic Quarks:

- While ordinary Helium-4 is stable, the **exotic quarks** like **top**, **strange**, and **charm** in our model would decay rapidly due to their instability. The **top quark**, for instance, decays via the weak force into a **W boson** and a **bottom quark**, while strange and charm quarks decay into lighter quarks like up and down.
- Such exotic configurations may exist **temporarily** in environments such as high-energy particle collisions (e.g., at the **Large Hadron Collider**) or astrophysical events (e.g., during supernovae or inside neutron stars). Still, they would quickly decay into standard quarks and return to a stable configuration.

7.2 Where Could This Exotic Helium-4 Exist?

The inclusion of exotic quarks suggests this helium configuration could exist **momentarily** in extreme environments:

- **Particle Colliders:** High-energy collisions at facilities like CERN's **Large Hadron Collider (LHC)** could produce these exotic quarks, momentarily creating an exotic helium-like structure before the exotic quarks decay.
- **Neutron Stars:** In the dense cores of neutron stars, exotic quarks (particularly strange quarks) might be present in what is known as **strange quark matter**.
- **Early Universe:** Shortly after the Big Bang, exotic quarks were more abundant, and configurations like this could have existed briefly before decaying into more stable forms of matter.

8. Conclusion:

This paper presents an in-depth analysis of the Helium-4 quark structure, including both core quarks (up and down) and exotic quarks (top, strange, and charm), using the dodecahedron framework. The **total energy of the system** has been recalculated to be **182,570 MeV**, with a significant portion of the energy attributed to the top quark, contributing **173,100 MeV**. Despite this intriguing configuration, it is expected that this exotic Helium-4 structure would be highly unstable in conventional environments due

to the short lifetimes of exotic quarks, particularly the top quark, which decays rapidly (on the order of 10^{-25} seconds).

While this structure may only exist momentarily in **high-energy environments** such as particle collisions (e.g., at the LHC) or possibly within **neutron stars** or during the early universe, its stability is heavily dependent on the **binding forces** mediated by gluons. Detailed lattice QCD simulations would be crucial for exploring the **gluon-mediated interactions, potential energy distribution**, and stability criteria further.

Future work should include **numerical simulations** to calculate the **binding energy** more accurately and assess the conditions under which this structure may exist. Additionally, studies into the **decay pathways** of exotic quarks and the influence of the strong coupling constant (α_s) at various energy scales will be critical to fully understanding the dynamics of such an exotic Helium-4 structure.

9. Observations: Potential Connection to Dark Matter and Dark Energy

Given the presence of **exotic quarks** in this Helium-4 structure, such as the **top, strange, and charm quarks**, this configuration may have interesting implications for dark matter and dark energy, especially in high-energy environments or extreme astrophysical contexts.

Exotic Quark Behavior and Dark Matter

Dark matter remains one of the biggest mysteries in modern physics. One of the leading hypotheses is that it could be composed of particles outside the Standard Model, such as heavy quarks or exotic matter. The presence of **top quarks** in the exotic Helium-4 configuration, which is much heavier than core quarks, suggests that such a structure could potentially contribute to dark matter-like behavior under certain conditions.

- **Mass Contribution to Dark Matter:** Given that **top quarks** contribute a large amount of mass to the structure ($\sim 173,100$ MeV), it's possible that such configurations, even if short-lived, could manifest in extreme environments, such as **neutron stars** or **primordial events**, where dark matter is hypothesized to form. If there is a mechanism that could stabilize such structures, they may

contribute to the unseen mass in the universe, which is currently attributed to dark matter.

- **Quark Matter and Dark Matter:** The potential existence of **quark matter** inside **neutron stars** or similar extreme environments aligns with certain dark matter models. In such a context, this exotic Helium-4 could behave in a way that mimics the effects of dark matter, especially if its quark-gluon interactions result in a weak interaction with ordinary matter, a hallmark of dark matter.

Gluon Dynamics and Dark Energy

Dark energy is another fundamental puzzle characterized by the accelerated expansion of the universe. While gluon interactions primarily govern the strong force, **exotic quark-gluon dynamics** within this Helium-4 structure might offer insights into **vacuum energy** or **energy densities** associated with dark energy.

- **Vacuum Energy and Gluon Fields:** The gluon-mediated binding forces in the dodecahedron framework of exotic Helium-4 could create **localized fluctuations** in the vacuum energy. If these fluctuations occur on a cosmic scale or in extreme astrophysical environments, they could contribute to the overall vacuum energy density, potentially influencing the **cosmological constant** associated with dark energy.
- **Strong Force Contributions to Cosmic Expansion:** Although the strong force operates on very small scales, the presence of exotic quarks and their high mass could imply **large-scale energy densities** under certain conditions. If exotic structures like this contribute to the vacuum energy, they may play a minor role in the overall equation of state that governs cosmic expansion.

Predictions and Future Research Directions

- **Astrophysical Tests:** If such exotic Helium-4 configurations exist momentarily in high-energy astrophysical events (e.g., in neutron stars or during early universe conditions), they might produce **detectable signatures** in particle accelerators or through **gravitational waves**, which could offer indirect evidence of their contribution to dark matter or dark energy.

- **Theoretical Models:** Further development of **beyond-Standard-Model (BSM) theories** might explore how exotic quark configurations could influence **cosmic structures**. Simulating the behavior of these quark-gluon dynamics at extreme scales could offer novel insights into the connections between the **strong force**, **vacuum energy**, and **cosmic expansion**.

This study of **exotic quark matter**, such as this Helium-4 structure, may provide novel insights into the mysteries of **dark matter** and **dark energy**. More detailed theoretical and experimental studies will be needed to explore these possibilities fully.

WORKING PAPER

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Appendix A: Tables for Helium-4 (He-4) Quark Structure

Table A1: Quark Energy Distribution

Quark	Type	Mass (MeV/c ²)	Quantity	Total Mass (MeV/c ²)
Up (u)	Core	335	12	4,020
Down (d)	Core	340	12	4,080
Top (t)	Exotic	173,100	1	173,100
Strange (s)	Exotic	95	1	95
Charm (c)	Exotic	1,275	1	1,275
Total	-	-	27	182,570

Table A2: Quark Charge Distribution

Quark	Type	Charge (e)	Quantity	Total Charge
Up (u)	Core	+2/3	12	+8
Down (d)	Core	-1/3	12	-4
Top (t)	Exotic	+2/3	1	+2/3
Strange (s)	Exotic	-1/3	1	-1/3
Charm (c)	Exotic	+2/3	1	+2/3
Total	-	-	27	+4

Table A3: Gluon Interaction Summary

Quark Pair	Interaction Type	Potential Energy (Short-Distance)	Potential Energy (Long-Distance)
Up - Down	Strong (Gluon)	-	σr
Up - Exotic (Top)	Strong (Gluon)	$-\frac{4}{3} \frac{\alpha_s}{r}$	σr
Down - Exotic (Strange, Charm)	Strong (Gluon)	$-\frac{4}{3} \frac{\alpha_s}{r}$	σr

Table A4: Strong Coupling Constant (α_s) at Different Energy Scales

Energy Scale (Q^2)	Strong Coupling Constant ($\alpha_s(Q^2)$)
Low Energy (< 1 GeV)	0.3
High Energy (> 10 GeV)	0.1

Table A5: Potential Decay Channels for Exotic Quarks

Exotic Quark	Decay Channel	Lifetime (s)
Top (t)	$t \rightarrow W^+ + b$	$\sim 10^{-25}$
Strange (s)	$s \rightarrow u + \mu^-$	$\sim 10^{-10}$
Charm (c)	$c \rightarrow s + W^+$	$\sim 10^{-13}$

Table A6: Overall Energy Summary

Energy Source	Total Energy (MeV)
Core Quarks (Up + Down)	8,100
Exotic Quarks (Top, Strange, Charm)	174,470
Total Energy	182,570

Summary of Tables

In **Appendix A**, we provide detailed tables on quark energy distribution (Table A1), charge distribution (Table A2), and gluon interactions (Table A3). We also present the strong coupling constant values at different energy scales (Table A4) and decay channels for exotic quarks (Table A5). The overall energy summary (Table A6) consolidates the total energy for the Helium-4 structure based on core and exotic quarks.